

FOLK GAMES THAT SERVE TO FORM COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS AND SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF THEIR ORGANIZATION

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Abstract: In this article, folk games that serve to form communicative competence of elementary school students are studied, the specific aspects of their organization are analyzed.

Key words: pedagogue, professional competence, classification, improvement, competence, competent approach, communicative, folk games.

INTRODUCTION. Currently, the tasks of reforming primary education, introducing new approaches to it, and implementing concepts affecting the quality and efficiency of education are becoming urgent. As one of the important approaches in this regard, there is an increasing need to integrate folk games into primary education, to use folk games in organizing the education of students. First of all, each game is structured in a simple, psychologically interesting way, and high human feelings such as nationalism, kindness, bravery, patriotism, tolerance, self-sacrifice are embedded in its essence.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Specialists have been paying special attention to the problem of using folk games and didactic lessons to improve the effectiveness of education. Among the scientists of our republic are M.Abdullajonova, B.R.Adizov, A.Y.Bobomurodova, O.Jamoldinova, B.Ziyomuhamedov, G.Ibragimova, R.Ishmuhamedov, U.I.Mahkamov, M.H.Mahmudov, O.Musurmonova, D.Sharipova, Sh.Sharipov, N.M.Egamberdiyeva. this was reflected in his works.

From foreign scientists A. Yolanda, N. Nicotera, A. Christopher, L. Botcheva, J. Shih, L. C. Huffman, L. D. Breeman, van Lier, Theo Wubbels, R. Sears, J. L. Spilt, E. Vervoort, A. Koenen, F. Clemente, A. Amutio, L. Gonzalez's studies have explored the possibilities of games in the formation of social skills and basic competencies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The technology of organizing and holding games has a special pedagogical significance as a whole. Including: a) didactically justifying the incomparable importance of games in the formation of friendly relations and communicative skills in students; b) create a basis for the classification of games according to forms of communication; c) has pedagogical possibilities, such as helping teachers to create an atmosphere of friendly relations among students by organizing games.

Below we will consider folk games that help to form communicative competence in elementary school students and their organization and playing procedure:

Jambil. In this game, students are divided into 2 groups. There are usually 5-6 players in each group. The players of the first group throw the ball at the stones placed in the cells from the specified distance. The number of stones in the cage is 4 t. If the stones in the cage fall when the ball is rolled, one of the players of the second group will guard the area around the cage with the ball. If the guard hits the first group of players with a ball when they approach to put the stones in the squares, that player is out of the game. If this group places

the stones correctly on the big ones, this group is considered to be the winner. If they can't, they lose. The game continues like this.

Rabbits, watchman and hunter. In this game, four rectangles (rabbit nests) are drawn on one side of the field, and a semicircle-guardhouse is drawn on the opposite side. A rope-wall is pulled at a height of 25-30 cm in the middle of the field. Children are divided into four groups and placed in four nests. In the guardhouse there are managers-guards and hunters. According to the teacher's signal, the rabbits leave their houses, climb over the wall and close to the pole. At the teacher's signal, the guard claps his hands three times, that is, "shoots". After the shot is fired, the guard and the hunter together chase the rabbits home. After the captures are counted, the hares return to their homes, and the guard and the hunter return to the guardhouse. The managers are replaced and the game is resumed.

A star. 6 children will participate in this game. This game is played in the form of a five-pointed star: one child stands at each corner, and the sixth is in the center. The child in the center says the name of a child around him and goes to the place of the child whose name is said. And the child whose name is said must walk towards the center. The one who goes first wins and leads the game. The one who doesn't get there leaves the game and is replaced by another child.

The chaser. In this game, the field is limited by a line. One guardian is appointed. Other players form a circle around him.

The progress of the game. The chaser says: "one-two-three." All the children run in all directions, the chaser chases and catches them. Runners can sit down in case of danger, those who sit down will not be caught by the chaser. A child caught by a chaser becomes a mother. You can play the game as long as you want.

The rule of the game.

1. The sitting time should not exceed 5 seconds, otherwise the chaser will catch him.
2. A sitting player is not caught.
3. The caught player must raise his hand and say "I became the chaser" and then he becomes the chaser. If he doesn't say he's caught, it doesn't count for him to be the chaser and finish off the others.

Instructions for the game. You can also play the "jump fight" version of this game. The game is played as described above. But a child who jumps on one leg will not be caught [5].

Passing the ball between the legs: 3-4 groups line up in front of the starting line. All groups stand in one-person columns, standing at a distance of 2-3 m from each other. The distance between the players is 1-2 steps, they should stand without bending their legs. The first players in the columns will have basketballs. They bend down and hold the ball on the ground. A group is given for everyone to bend over. Players bend down and prepare to pass the ball between their legs. When the signal is given, the first player rolls the ball back between his legs.

Pass the ball over the head. Players are divided into 2-4 groups. Each group stands separately in columns of one person (the distance between them is 2-3). The distance between the column players is as close as possible, but not more than one step. The first players of each group have volleyball or basketball balls in their hands. All players raise their hands up. After the teacher gives a signal, the players pass the balls over their heads to the players standing behind them, etc. When the players at the end of the column receive the ball,

they run from the right side of their group, stand first in front of the column and pass the ball over their heads.

Shepherd (Uzbek folk game). In this game, a line is drawn on two opposite sides of the field. Players are divided into two groups, and each group faces each other behind the line on both sides of the field. A leader is elected for each group. Each player of the first (starting) group has a piece of paper and tape.

The progress of the game. The head of the first group (starting the game) looks at the head of the second group and says: "Shepherd, shepherd." The leader of the second group says: "Your herd is gone." "Who did my herd reach?" asks the head of the first group. The mother of the second group answers by saying the name of a child she wants from the first group, for example: "Your herd reached Karim." The two groups quickly switch places, while the players of the second group have to catch Kareem, that is, touch him, and the players of the first group have to save Kareem, that is, give him a tape while running. The game is replayed 4-6-8 times so that both teams can start the game evenly. The group with the most players wins the game.

The rule of the game. 1. Only the named player and the player trying to give him a tape can be caught. 2. The caught child goes to the players of the second group without saying a word. 3. A player whose hand is touched before reaching the line during the transition to the second side is considered caught [4].

Throwing games. In this game, students hold hands and form separate circles in their divisions. It is recommended to have 8-10 students in each circle. The distance between students is 3-4 steps, they stand facing the circle. A line is drawn on the inside of the circles, and players cannot enter from this line during the game. Parents holding basketballs or volleyballs stand in the middle of the circles. Each student will have his own number. For example, first, second, third and so on. When the teacher gives a signal, the head teacher passes the ball to the first player and takes it back from him, then passes it to the second, and so on. Onaboshi, after receiving the ball from the last player, holds it up. This means the game is over. The teacher announces which circle has won. A new boss appears in the middle and the game continues again. If during the game the ball falls out of his hand and goes to the other side, the player who dropped the ball must catch up with him and return to his place with the ball, and only then pass the ball to the head coach. possible

Don't give the ball to the mother: Students hold hands and stand in a circle. They let go of their hands and take two steps back. The manager stands in the middle of the circle. One of the players has a volleyball in his hand. When the signal is given, the players pass the ball to each other so that the manager does not take it away. The manager tries to touch the ball. If he can touch the ball, he will exchange places with the guilty player. If the manager cannot touch the ball for a long time, a second manager can be placed next to him. The number of players in the circle should not exceed 10-12. If there are many players, it is necessary to form several circles [3].

Ball race. In this game, all players form a circle. Two players facing each other in the circle are given a volleyball.

The progress of the game. When the teacher gives the signal, the players holding the ball pass the ball to the child next to them, who takes the ball and, in turn, passes it to the child next to them, etc.

Game rules.

1. You can pass the ball only to the child next to you.
2. It is not possible to pass the ball to his neighbor, leaving the child next to him. If the ball falls to the ground, the game starts again.

Instructions for the game. If there are many players, they can be divided into two circles, and each circle can play independently.

Day and night. This game is played on the field or in the hall. Two parallel lines are drawn in the center of the field 1-2 steps apart. Lines are drawn parallel to both lines on opposite sides of the field at a distance of 15-20 steps. Players are divided into two equal groups and spend time in the middle of the hall with their backs to each other (leaving a distance between them). A line is drawn behind each sheren. Do not cross this line before running. one of the groups will be "night" and the other "day".

The progress of the game. The teacher suddenly shouted "day!" says, upon hearing this word, the "night" group starts running towards their home. "Kun" group chases him. Then he returns home. The caught players are counted and identified by the teacher, and then sent to their group. The teacher calls one or another group again. The game is repeated 6-8 times for each group to chase each other equally. After the end of the game, the caught players are counted. The group that caught more players wins the game.

The qualities characteristic of the culture, traditions and values of our people are embodied in each of the national folk games. For example, in the game of "tug of war", mutual team spirit, harmony; honesty, bravery in a wrestling match; dexterity, left-handedness in equestrian competitions; In the "hide and seek" game, ingenuity and vigilance are cultivated. That is why it is necessary for teachers and trainers to choose the right folk games during training and to organize them effectively from an educational point of view. After all, "it is very important to choose the right game and conduct it according to the purpose. But the game does not always solve educational tasks. In order to achieve a good result in the field of education, action games should be educationally organized and conducted. The leader of the game should know the student team well, be familiar with the content and rules of each game, and have high pedagogical skills. Only then will he be able to achieve the educational and educational goals of action games" [2].

In fact, folk games are characterized not only by physically training students, but also by providing them with high moral education. Especially in team games, the participants strive for victory based on the principle of "one person for all", make up for each other's shortcomings, and help each other in difficult situations. Students develop tolerance, harmony and cohesion. decides the criteria. Games such as "White poplar, blue poplar", "Geese and swans", "Strong and agile", "Tug of war", "Quvlashmachok" can be included among such games. And the games "Durra", "Atib kochar", "Uchtalik toptash", "Hakkalakam condition", "Otambakala-Qaqbosh", "Ikki tash", "Nongog urish", "Beshtash" [1] It educates the qualities of mutual compromise, agreement, and unity among followers.

"Merganlik" can also be said to be one of those games. Its peculiarity is that more boys play it, and they learn the skills of accurate aiming and prepare for the future defense of the homeland. There are variants of this game that can be played with different tools. There are forms that are organized with a ball, with a stone, with various sticks or other objects. The participant of the game looks at the people gathered around him and says, "Well, who shot again?" It's: "Who else will throw this ball into the goal?" means and invites fans to the game. Enthusiastic aspirants try to knock down the light plastic shapes with a soft and light, fluffy

ball, which are picked at a distance of three to four meters, and they diligently throw the balls at the target. But the ball is very light, it either misses the target after a thousand shots, or the direction of the air takes it in another direction. You see, a sniper makes mistakes. Unsatisfied, the sniper will try again and again.

This interesting game can be applied to school activities. For this, you just need to make shapes from fluffy balls and plastic. This game can be played in any discipline. With this, students have:

- mental and mental fatigue is eliminated;
- interest in training increases;
- high mood and cheerfulness appear;
- the qualities of creativity, initiative, inquisitiveness are formed;
- the principle of working as a team is decided, etc.

In general, the use of folk games in training shows the following results:

1. Pupils' interest in life is increasing.
2. Their creativity and motivation to create is growing.
3. The desire to respect peers and friends, to help them in difficult times is awakening.
4. Pupils are getting used to being fair, honest and honest people.
5. Regularly playing sports turns the use of folk games into a daily activity not only in class, but also in the family.
6. An atmosphere of mutual harmony and friendly relations is created among students, and the skills of treating adults with respect and honor with children are being formed.
7. Feelings of pride in one's ancestors, national values, great past and courage of our people are being formed [1].

A well-chosen game is an important condition for the success of education and training. When preparing for the game, it is necessary to determine the main tasks of the lesson, taking into account the composition, age characteristics, as well as physical fitness of the participants in the game.

When choosing a game, the teacher should know how the training will be conducted (if it is conducted in the style of a lesson, whether the game will be conducted in its first, second or final part, during a break, etc.). The venue, weather and temperature should be taken into account. If the game is held in winter, it is appropriate to choose more active games that activate students and evenly distribute the physical load.

CONCLUSION. School holidays are the most effective factor in creating a healthy and cheerful mood in students. It should also be taken into account that more students will participate in such ceremonies. Therefore, public games such as "White poplar, blue poplar", "Pat", "Pr-r-r...", "Circling whip", "Walking to music" to the sound of music, or It is necessary to make the game more lively and interesting with the help of music. One-on-one competitions, dexterity and fast running competitions of elementary school students can be organized through games such as "Tort the tape", "Tortaga", "Who is strong and agile".

In conclusion, high attention paid by teachers and coaches to playing national folk games in activities in primary education, extracurricular activities, national folk games in various forms, educational should be organized according to the wishes and interests of the people.

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